

Review

Gibbons 400 Festival, *Chelys Consort of Viols*, *Viola da Gamba Society*, *Choir of St John's College*, Oxford, St John's College, Oxford, 7–9 March 2025.

John Bryan

Chelys Consort of Viols are to be congratulated for the three-day festival (March 7–9) they arranged in Oxford to celebrate Orlando Gibbons and his musical legacy, on the 400th anniversary of his death. The festival included three concerts of Gibbons' music for viols, voices and keyboard, as well as an organ masterclass with Christian Wilson, and a service of music and readings for Lent at St John's College, Oxford. St John's proved to be a most welcoming venue for the whole event, and an appropriate one considering the connections with Gibbons' output, which includes the verse anthem *This Is The Record of John* 'made for Dr Laud president of Saint Johns' (Oxford, Christ Church Mus. 21). Chelys collaborated with David Bannister (the college's Choir Director), his choir *Vespri Segreti*, and the chapel choir in performances that included *This Is The Record of John* alongside other music.

Another organisation collaborating in the festival was the Viola da Gamba Society, whose series of events on the Saturday was attended by around fifty members and started in the College's comfortable Mark Bedingham Room with a presentation on 'Beauty and Expression in Orlando Gibbons' Recreational Song'. This was given by Katie Bank, Leverhulme Early Career Fellow in the Department of History, University of Birmingham. Combining her academic interests in music's connections with literature and the visual culture of early modern Britain, and her practical experience as a singer, she was able to give us a multi-faceted approach to understanding the context in which Gibbons composed his Mottets and Madrigals of 1612 and his verse anthems for domestic spiritual exercise. Drawing on a wide range of examples of the omnipresence of musical imagery in the decoration of wealthier homes, and the links between these and literary sources that comment on the power of music to affect the emotions, she suggested that singers of Gibbons' music (and of course the viol players working with them) would have probably had a nexus of non-musical references in mind.

Katie Bank then examined two very different examples of Gibbons' vocal music in some detail, beginning with 'The Cries of London', which she saw as an example of how the performers of Gibbons' time wished to emulate the freedom of those represented (street vendors, working people such as boatsmen and chimney sweeps) who seemed free to sing as they worked, whereas those involved in 'higher matters' (those able to buy sets of viols and purchase music) might feel restricted by protocols of behaviour that limited their freedom. She then investigated the extraordinary text of 'See, see, the Word is incarnate', 'made by Doctor Goodman De[an]: of Rochester' (Oxford, Christ Church Mus. 21), and the intensity of Gibbons' musical response to it. Highlighted were the fact that this condensation of the main events in the life, death and resurrection of Christ (which takes little more than six minutes to perform) is told in the present tense and in effect consists of a series of 'headlines' which fall rapidly one after another. This gives the meaning an immediacy that is similar to the

sometimes violent imagery of contemporary religious texts and imagery, and is so effectively portrayed in Gibbons' matchless musical setting.

Before lunch the meeting moved to the College Chapel in St. John's for a short recital by Sarah Small and Timothy Lin, who met as postgraduate performers at the Royal College of Music and perform together as the ensemble Hex, as well as freelancing with other groups. The recital was one of an on-going series promoted by the Viola da Gamba Society to offer younger professional viol players a platform. Their Gibbons offering was a couple of his playful yet intricate two-part fantasias for treble viols (Cambridge, King's College MSS Rowe 112-3). Each then played a virtuosic solo: Sarah gave us Tobias Hume's 'Good againe' (The First Part of Ayres, 1605) while Timothy scaled the heights and depths of Alfonso Ferrabosco's monumental viola bastarda divisions on 'Sound out my voyce', the English version of Palestrina's famous madrigal 'Vestiva i colli' (Oxford, Bodleian Mus.Sch.D.246-7). He thus managed to combine a composer who worked alongside Gibbons at the Stuart court with the other composer celebrating his centenary in 2025. Together the players presented sets of divisions for two bass viols by Christopher Simpson and John Jenkins, all performed with great dexterity and a compelling sense of musical direction.

For the afternoon session the meeting transferred to the spectacular surroundings of the Upper Library of Christ Church College, where we were warmly welcomed by the College Librarian and Library Assistant, Dr Samuel Teague, the latter of which gave an overview of the library's music collection. This proved to be an excellent prelude to Jonathan Wainwright, Emeritus Professor of Music at the University of York, who gave us a compelling survey of the library's holdings of Orlando Gibbons' music, much of which was tantalisingly displayed behind him. He began with the printed set of part-books of Motets and Madrigals (Oxford, Christ Church Mus. 708-12) with their lavish bindings copiously decorated in gold and bearing the crest of Sir Christopher Hatton (c.1570-1638) their dedicatee. It was plausibly suggested that this particular set was that presented by the composer his patron, and there was certainly a frisson in the room as they were held aloft!

Jonathan Wainwright continued by explaining the central importance of the Hatton family as collectors of music, much of it forming the nucleus of the earlier material in the Christ Church music library. The main protagonist was Gibbons' patron's son, also Christopher, later 1st Baron Hatton, who spent prodigiously acquiring printed collections of motets and madrigals from Italy, some of them remarkably up-to-date in composition, but also employed important scribes to copy large amounts of English music that includes many unique survivors of pieces by Orlando Gibbons. Among these is the score book Christ Church Mus. 21 which contains many of Gibbons' fantasias, as well as verse anthems and versions of material from the Motets and Madrigals mostly copied without texts and some titled 'Fantazie'. The Christ Church holdings of music by Gibbons include two of the three engraved part-books containing Fantazies of III. parts published c. 1621 (Mus. 105-6). Then there is the 'Great Set' (Mus. 2, 397-408 and 436) which contains several of Gibbons' three- and six-part fantasias.

Once Jonathan Wainwright had concluded his impressive review of the material on the table behind him, we were encouraged to take a closer look, aided by the librarians who were happy to turn folios for us to inspect particular pages and pieces that interested us. For many of the members present this was the closest they had been to the working materials containing the music they so often played, and I'm sure many felt closer than ever to one of our most loved composers of music 'for the viols'.